

which on recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid melted at 310° . This was found to be 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone already referred to. (Found: N, 13.33. $C_{13}H_{10}N_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent).

The insoluble product was crystallised from alcohol when it melted at 266° , the m. p. being not depressed when admixed with the compound 3-cyano-1:4-dimethyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone previously obtained by reacting benzoylacetoneamine with cyanoacetmethylamide.

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Dimercaptothiobiazole as an Analytical Reagent.

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In a note published previously (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 403) by one of us (J.G.) reference was made to the use of

dimercaptothiobiazole or thiobiazole-1:4-dithiol $\begin{array}{c} \text{N} \text{---} \text{N} \\ \parallel \quad \quad \parallel \\ \text{HS} \cdot \text{C} \quad \text{C} \cdot \text{SH} \\ \quad \quad \quad \text{S} \end{array}$ as a

very convenient reagent for the estimation of copper, lead and bismuth, and for their separation from the metals of the II B group and the rest of the analytical groups (*e.g.*, As, Sb, Sn, Mo, Fe, Zn, etc.). Mention was also made of its usefulness as a qualitative micro-reagent for Cu and Bi.

The substance behaves as a weak acid like H_2S , the hydrogen atoms of the sulphydryl groups being replaceable by metals under suitable conditions. It gives characteristic coloured precipitates with most of the elements of the H_2S -group of the analytical table. The precipitates obtained in most of these cases were, however, of variable composition and could not, therefore, be directly weighed, but they settled readily and were easily separated by filtration.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the reagent.—Thiobiazole-1:4-dithiol was most conveniently prepared according to the methods described by

Losanitsch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2544) from carbon disulphide and hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic ammonia and was purified by recrystallisation from ether, m.p. (Losanitsch), 168°; m.p. (found), 168-69°. A solution of the ammonium salt of the reagent was used in the estimations.

The substance is slightly soluble in cold water, more in hot, but easily soluble in dilute ammonia and alcohol. An aqueous solution of the reagent behaves with some of the soluble metallic salts in the following way :

TABLE I.

Salts of.	Behaviour.	
Copper	Insoluble brown precipitate, turns granular in presence of mineral acids.	
Cadmium	Yellowish white crystalline precipitate, soluble in acids.	
Lead	Bright yellow granular precipitate, insoluble in very dilute nitric acid and in organic acids like acetic and tartaric.	
Bismuth	Bright red precipitate, insoluble in very dilute nitric acid and in organic acids, but soluble in dilute HCl.	
Silver	Dirty white granular precipitate, insoluble in very dilute nitric acid.	
Mercury	Yellow precipitate, insoluble in nitric acid.	
Arsenic Antimony Tin (stannous)	} Yellow precipitate, partly soluble on heating.	
Zinc		Sparingly soluble white precipitate, readily soluble in mineral acids.
Thorium		Yellow crystalline precipitate, soluble in excess of the reagent (cf. Losanitsch, <i>loc. cit.</i>).

Detection and Estimation of Copper.

For sensitiveness and identification limits, a dilute hydrochloric acid solution of the salt and an aqueous solution of the reagent were used. The salt used was copper sulphate.

Precipitation limit = 1 part in 1,600,000 parts.

Colouration limit = 1 part in 6,500,000 parts.

Identification limit = 0.02 μ g.

(One μ g is one millionth part of a gram = 1 microgram = γ).

As the composition of the copper precipitate was variable, the metal was estimated volumetrically by decomposing the moist precipitate with nitric acid (1:1 by volume). The solution was filtered from any undissolved sulphur, and evaporated to a small bulk (5 c.c.), after the addition of a little bromine water, to remove all nitrous acid and most of the nitric acid. Copper was then estimated iodometrically in the usual way.

Separation of Copper from Iron.

A solution of copper sulphate (Kahlbaum, "Pro Analyti") of approximately 1 % Cu was prepared and the copper content was determined by the Quinaldinate method (Rây and Bose, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, 95, 400). A solution of ferric chloride of about the same strength was also prepared from the chemically pure salt, and its iron content was determined by analysis.

A mixture of the known volumes of the two solutions was warmed with sulphurous acid to reduce the iron to the ferrous state and thus to avoid an undesirable precipitation of the condensation product of the reagent, as ferric chloride oxidises the dithiol to disulphide. The solution was diluted to a volume of 180-200 c.c., acidified with 5-15 c.c. of 2N-H₂SO₄ (more acid is not harmful), heated to boiling; and to this the reagent (solution of the ammonium salt of the dithiol) was added, drop by drop, with constant stirring. After allowing the precipitate to settle, the solution was filtered hot, washed several times by decantation with hot water, finally transferred and washed free from sulphate. The moist precipitate was then transferred to the same beaker in which it was contained, decomposed with nitric acid (1:1) and estimated iodometrically with N/20-Na₂S₂O₃. Iron was estimated in the filtrate by decomposing the reagent with a little bromine water, boiling off the excess of bromine and precipitating the metal as hydroxide. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

	Metals present.	Metals found.	Error.
1.	Cu, 0.0528 g. Fe, 0.1192	Cu, 0.0530 g. Fe, 0.1193	+ 0.0002 + 0.0001
2.	Cu, 0.0528 Fe, 0.0596	Cu, 0.0528 ...	Nil ...
3.	Cu, 0.0528 Fe, 0.1192	Cu, 0.0530 ...	+ 0.0002 ...
4.	Cu, 0.0211 Fe, 0.1192	Cu, 0.0212 Fe, 0.1192	+ 0.0001 Nil
5.	Cu, 0.0845 Fe, 0.0596	Cu, 0.0845 Fe, 0.0596	" "
6.	Cu, 0.0792 Fe, 0.0358	Cu, 0.0792 Fe, 0.0358	" "
7.	Cu, 0.0211 Fe, 0.1192	Cu, 0.0212 Fe, 0.1193	+ 0.0001 + 0.0001
8.	Cu, 0.0106 Fe, 0.2384	Cu, 0.0106 ...	Nil ...

Separation of Copper from Zinc.

The zinc solution was prepared by dissolving chemically pure zinc sulphate in water containing a little free sulphuric acid. The strength of the solution was determined by estimating zinc as zinc ammonium phosphate.

A mixture of the known volumes of copper and zinc solutions was diluted to 180-200 c.c. and acidified with 5 c.c. of 1:4 (by volume) sulphuric acid. The solution was heated to boiling and the copper precipitated as before. The precipitate was first washed with hot water containing a little dilute sulphuric acid, and then with hot water alone. Copper was estimated from the moist precipitate as described previously. The filtrate was treated with bromine water to decompose the reagent, concentrated to about 350 c.c., and the zinc precipitated and estimated as zinc ammonium phosphate. The results are tabulated below :

TABLE III.

Metals present.	Metals found.	Error.
1. Cu, 0.0528 g. Zn, 0.0976	Cu, 0.0528 g. Zn, 0.0977	Nil + 0.0001
2. Cu, 0.0739 Zn, 0.0488	Cu, 0.0740 Zn, 0.0488	+ 0.0001 Nil
3. Cu, 0.0317 Zn, 0.0976	Cu, 0.0317 Zn, 0.0976	Nil Nil
4. Cu, 0.1056 Zn, 0.0195	Cu, 0.1055 Zn, 0.0195	- 0.0001 Nil
5. Cu, 0.0739 Zn, 0.0683	Cu, 0.0740 Zn, 0.0683	+ 0.0001 Nil

Separation of Copper from Arsenic (tri-and pentavalent).

Separation was effected in the presence of ammonium fluoride to prevent any precipitation of arsenic by the reagent. The copper and arsenic solutions were mixed, and fifteen times the weight of ammonium fluoride, as there was arsenic present, were added. The solution was diluted to about 180 c.c., acidified with 5 c.c. of 2N-H₂SO₄ (more acid is not harmful), and the copper was precipitated as usual. The precipitate was twice decanted with hot water containing at first a small quantity of ammonium fluoride, then with hot water alone. The precipitate was dissolved in nitric acid and treated as usual,

TABLE IV.

Cu present.	As added.	Cu found.	Error.
1. 0.0528 g.	0.05 g.	0.0528 g.	Nil
2. 0.0739	0.015	0.0736	-0.0003
3. 0.0211	0.10	0.0211	Nil

The estimation of arsenic in the filtrate was deemed unnecessary as a check, as its presence in the copper precipitate would vitiate the titration value.

Separation of Copper from Antimony (tri-and pentavalent).

As in the case of arsenic, the separation was effected in the presence of ammonium fluoride which forms a complex ion with antimony preventing its precipitation by the reagent.

The amount of fluoride added was approximately fifteen times the weight of antimony present. The volume of the solution was diluted to about 180 c.c. and the copper was precipitated in the usual way. The washing and further treatment of the precipitate was exactly similar to those employed in the case of arsenic-copper separation.

TABLE V.

Sb added.	Cu present.	Cu found.	Error.
1. 0.06 g.	0.0528 g.	0.0529 g.	+0.0001
2. 0.02	0.0739	0.0739	Nil
3. 0.11	0.0211	0.0211	Nil

The antimony in the filtrate can be estimated after decomposing the fluoride by heating with boric acid.

Separation of Copper from Tin (stannic).

The separation of copper from stannic tin is rendered easier by the fact that tartaric acid prevents the precipitation of tin by the reagent.

A solution of stannic tin was prepared by dissolving chemically pure tin in potassium chlorate and hydrochloric acid. The strength of the solution was determined by estimating the tin as dioxide.

Known volumes of copper and tin solutions were mixed. 4.5 G. of solid tartaric acid were added to the mixture and the solution diluted to 150—200 c.c. This was rendered strongly acidic with

1 c.c. of concentrated HCl, and the copper precipitated and estimated in the usual way.

Tin in the filtrate was estimated by precipitating with H_2S in hot solution, washing and igniting the sulphide to dioxide, at first very carefully, and finally over the blast-lamp.

TABLE VI

Metals present.	Metals found.	Error.
1. Cu, 0.0528 g. Sn, 0.1215	Cu, 0.0527 g. —	-0.0001 —
2. Cu, 0.0317 Sn, 0.0632	Cu, 0.0317 Sn, 0.0629	Nil -0.0003
3. Cu, 0.0211 Sn, 0.1265	Cu, 0.0211 Sn, 0.1271	Nil +0.0006
4. Cu, 0.0528 Sn, 0.1265	Cu, 0.0530 —	+0.0002 —
5. Cu, 0.0422 Sn, 0.0759	Cu, 0.0422 —	Nil —
6. Cu, 0.0211 Sn, 0.0632	Cu, 0.0211 Sn, 0.0632	Nil Nil
7. Cu, 0.0739 Sn, 0.0379	Cu, 0.0743 Sn, 0.0382	+0.0004 +0.0003
8. Cu, 0.0528 Sn, 0.0632	Cu, 0.0528 —	Nil —

The estimation of tin as oxide by igniting the sulphide is known to give invariably high results. The separation of stannous tin is also easily effected in the presence of ammonium fluoride, as described under antimony.

Separation of copper from molybdenum was easily effected as the reagent does not give any precipitate with molybdenum in acid solutions. The total volume of the solution varied from 160—200 c.c. and was acidified with 5—10 c.c. of 2N- H_2SO_4 . A large excess of the reagent should be avoided, as this causes reduction of molybdenum, which is difficult to wash away completely from the precipitate. The method of procedure was similar to those already described, only that the reagent solution should be more dilute. The precipitate was first washed with hot water containing a little sulphuric acid, and finally with hot water alone.

TABLE VII.

	Mo added.	Cu present.	Cu found.	Error.
1.	0.05 g.	0.0528 g.	0.0528 g.	Nil.
2.	0.01	0.0739	0.0739	"
3.	0.10	0.0211	0.0211	"

Separation of copper from tungsten.—Tungsten gives no precipitate with the reagent in acid solutions, but there is a tendency for the tungstic acid itself to separate out. On the other hand, the precipitate of copper obtained in neutral solutions is not easily filtrable. Hence a solution, rather dilute with respect to tungstic acid, was employed. Of the mineral acids, sulphuric acid was found to hold tungstic acid fairly well in solution. The volume of the solution was made up to 160—270 c.c. and acidified with 5 c.c. of 2N-H₄SO₄. The precipitate was first washed twice with hot water containing a little dilute sulphuric acid, and finally with hot water alone. The copper was estimated as usual.

TABLE VIII.

	W added.	Cu present.	Cu found.	Error.
1.	0.05 g.	0.0528 g.	0.0527 g.	-0.0001
2.	0.02	0.0739	0.0739	Nil

Solutions, more concentrated with respect to tungstic acid, cause precipitation of the latter.

Estimation of lead.—Lead was precipitated from a solution containing tartaric or acetic acid in the form of a dense bright yellow precipitate, easily filtrable. The precipitate was washed, dried partially for 10—15 minutes in an air-oven, and most of it was transferred and kept on a covered watch-glass. The filter-paper was gently heated in an open crucible over a low flame till the paper was completely consumed. The whole of the precipitate was then transferred into the crucible, treated with concentrated HNO₃ on the water-bath, covering the crucible with a watch-glass. After the decomposition of the precipitate and evaporation of most of the nitric acid, the residue was carefully evaporated with sulphuric acid. The last traces of the acid were removed by heating the crucible in a larger crucible, and the lead sulphate weighed.

Separation of lead from tin (stannic).—Extra pure lead acetate was dissolved in water containing free acetic acid. The strength of the solution was determined by evaporating a known volume of the solution to dryness with dilute sulphuric acid. Known volumes of lead and tin solutions of definite strength were mixed. Ammonium tartrate (3—5 g.) was added and the solution diluted. This was then rendered alkaline with ammonia when any precipitate previously formed dissolved completely. The solution was afterwards made slightly acidic

to litmus by the addition of acetic or tartaric acid. Excess of the latter should be carefully avoided as it precipitates the acid tartrate. The solution was then diluted to 150 c.c., heated to boiling, and the lead was precipitated by the gradual addition of the reagent (solution of the ammonium salt of the dithiol) with stirring. The precipitate was allowed to settle for 5 minutes, washed twice by decantation with hot water containing a little tartaric acid, and finally with hot water alone. The precipitate was then further treated as described above.

TABLE IX.

	Sn present.	Pb present.	Pb found.	Error.
1.	0.05 g.	0.0431 g.	0.0431 g.	Nil
2.	0.10	0.0172	0.0172	„
3.	0.015	0.0603	0.0601	-0.0002

Separation of lead from antimony (tri- and pentavalent) was effected in the presence of fluoride. To the mixed solution of lead and antimony, ammonium tartrate (3—5 g.) was added to prevent the precipitation of lead fluoride, and the solution then made slightly ammoniacal. This was diluted to 200 c.c., and fifteen times the weight of ammonium fluoride, as there was antimony present, were added. The solution was then rendered slightly acidic with tartaric or acetic acid, and the lead precipitated from the hot solution as usual. The precipitate after standing for five minutes was filtered, washed first with hot water containing a little fluoride, then with hot water alone. It was dried and estimated in the usual way.

TABLE X.

	Sb present.	Pb present.	Pb found.	Error.
1.	0.05 g.	0.0431 g.	0.0433 g.	+0.0002
2.	0.10	0.0172	0.0173	+0.0001
3.	0.015	0.0603	0.0605	+0.0002

The slightly high results are evidently due to the action of fluorides on the glass beaker, this can be prevented by using normal sodium fluoride.

Separation of Lead from Molybdenum and Alkaline Earths.

From molybdenum.—To the mixed solution of lead and molybdenum, ammonium tartrate (3—5 g.) added, and the solution rendered feebly acidic to litmus, It was diluted to about 200 c c. and the lead precipitated from the hot solution as usual, avoiding an unnecessary excess of the reagent. The precipitate was treated as usual and weighed as lead sulphate.

From the alkaline earths.—This separation was effected in acetic acid solution. The mixed solution was diluted to about 180 c.c., glacial acetic acid (2—10 c.c.) added, and as usual lead was precipitated and weighed as lead sulphate.

TABLE XI.

	Metals present.	Pb present.	Pb found.	Error.
1.	Mo, 0.05 g.	0.0431 g.	0.0431 g.	Nil
2.	0.015	0.0603	0.0603	„
3.	0.10	0.0172	0.0172	„
4.	Ca, Sr, Ba 0.20	0.0431	0.0431	„

Detection and Separation of Bismuth.

On account of the bright red colour of the precipitate, bismuth can be detected by means of the reagent in presence of all other elements except copper. The only other possible interfering elements are lead, arsenic, antimony, tin and mercury which give coloured precipitates. The precipitation of arsenic, antimony and tin, if present, was prevented by the addition of alkali fluoride. The detection in presence of mercury and lead was carried out by adding a dilute solution of the reagent, drop by drop, to a dilute nitric acid solution of the metals.

The test is extremely sensitive. A very dilute nitric acid solution of bismuth and an aqueous solution of the dithiol were used :

Precipitation limit = 1 part in 200,000 parts.

Colouration limit = 1 part in 1,600,000 parts.

Identification limit = 0.1 μ g.

Dübsky and Okac (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1934, **96**, 267) obtained the following values in hydrochloric acid solution of bismuth :

Sensitivity = 1 part in 28,000 parts.

Identification limit = 0.0012 mg. or 1.2 μ g.

These values confirm the observation that the bismuth precipitate has a slight solubility in hydrochloric acid.

In acid solution the bismuth precipitate does not give any constant composition—a fact confirmed by Dübsky and Okac (*loc. cit.*). They, however, claim to have obtained a substance of definite composition, having the chemical formula $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_2\text{HN}_2\text{S}_3)_3$, by precipitating a faintly acid solution of bismuth nitrate with the reagent, neutralised with two molar proportions of KOH.

Bismuth has been found to be completely precipitated from solutions containing even excess of tartaric acid or ammonium fluoride. The solutions should not contain free mineral acids, but should be acidified with weak acids like acetic or tartaric. This affords a quantitative separation of bismuth from arsenic, antimony, tin and molybdenum.

SUMMARY.

1. Some insoluble salts of dimercaptothiobiazole have been described.
2. The precipitation, colouration and identification limits of Cu- and Bi-compounds have been determined.
3. Copper has been separated from As, Sb, Sn, Mo, W, Fe, Zn and all metals of group III (analytical) and succeeding groups.
4. Lead has been separated from As, Sb, Sn, Mo and alkaline earths in presence of tartaric acid and alkali fluoride.
5. The utility of dimercaptothiobiazole as a qualitative micro-reagent for Bi has been stressed, and the possibility of separating the latter quantitatively from As, Sb, Sn and Mo has been indicated.